

The effect of serial correlation on sailing ship extreme responses.

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Abstract. The effect of the serial correlation on typical ship responses is evaluated in the North-Atlantic, which corresponds to design standards. The metocean data used in this work are based on a state-of-the-art global hindcast model synchronized with ship positions (AIS). The combination of the two datasets provides a representative time series of metocean variables (significant wave height and wave period here) encountered by sailing vessels. Using such a time trace, long-term extremes can be calculated using the serial correlation information and compared to scatter-diagram approaches that do not include this information. Discarding the sea states temporal dependence leads to conservative estimates, consistently with the literature. For the various responses investigated here, for the typical return period of 25 years, the amount of overestimation ranges from 0% to 15% depending on the responses. In addition, the differences between the responses are simply explained by their characteristic period. Responses sensitive to short waves show less long-term variability, which in turn leads to a small effect of the serial correlation. On the other hand, the effect of the serial correlation is found to be larger for responses excited by long waves. Finally, a pragmatic way of correcting the results from the scatter-diagram approach is proposed.

1. Introduction

Accurate extreme wave loads estimates are essential to the ship design process. Improvements in extreme loads assessment lead to optimised structures (safe and not overdesigned).

In the maritime industry practice, the long-term load distribution is generally based on long-term climate statistics described as the joint probability of significant wave height and period [IACS, 2022]. In using such scatter-diagrams, the information about the serial correlation of encountered sea-state is lost.

Theoretical aspects of the serial correlation effect on extremes have been investigated in several papers, see for instance [Beirlant et al., 2004, Mackay et al., 2021]. The current work aims to quantify those effects on typical ship responses and to calibrate a pragmatic approach to correct results based on scatter-diagrams.

As an illustration of the serial correlation problem, Figure 1. shows the long-term distribution of significant wave height encountered by sailing ships in the North-Atlantic, assuming independent sea states; next is the time history of the vessel experiencing the worst significant wave height in our database (details to come in the following sections). We observe that the four largest observations are actually encountered by this single vessel, in the same storm. The tail of the long-term distribution in Figure 1. is thus made of highly correlated data.

Note that the issue is not really in the correlation in the data used to create the scatter-diagram, but in the dependence of sea states actually encountered by vessels. Randomly sub-sampling the time series so that the scatter diagram is made of independent data (as in Vanem [2016]) does not solve the problem: assuming an infinitely long time trace, the scatter diagram obtained with or without sub-sampling is identical and would thus lead to the same long-term extreme estimate.

We start the paper by describing the data used in the analysis. Then, we describe the approaches used to assess the long-term extreme with and without accounting for the serial correlation. The results of the different approaches are presented, compared and discussed. Eventually, a pragmatic approach is proposed to correct the results obtained by a scatter-diagram approach.

Results discussed here are specific to typical global ship responses (more formally, responses for which the use of Rayleigh for the short-term cycles extrema distribution is ok).

Figure 1. Illustration of the serial correlation issue.

2. Data

2.1. Meteocean condition

The wave data used in the current paper are the ones underlying the IACS wave standard [IACS, 2022]. Hindcast dataset IOWAGA [Rascle and Ardhuin, 2013] is used together with AIS position database [Austefjord et al., 2023]. AIS data with sufficient fleet coverage is available since 2013 and was collected until 2021, 7 full years of data are used in the current work.

The result is significant wave height and periods encountered by ships. These data can be binned and distributed as compact scatter-diagram, easily used for long-term assessment (see Section 3.1.). There is, however, a downside to this binning process: the serial correlation information is lost. In the current work, in addition to the scatter-diagram, we use the original data.

The original data contains records of sea states encountered by thousands of different vessels, in North-Atlantic area, as defined in IACS [2022]. To organise those data in a meaningful time-series which includes the serial correlation information, the following processing is used:

1. The records are grouped per vessel and re-sampled with a 3h step.
2. For each vessel, the records are ordered in time and split into voyages. The voyage boundaries correspond to the vessel entering and leaving the North-Atlantic area.
3. The voyages for all ships are concatenated in a single time-trace.

The time trace thus obtained is considered to reasonably represent the serial correlation of sea-state encountered by sailing vessels. Figure 2. illustrates the H_s observed along randomly picked voyages in 2018 (among the 150606 voyages available in the dataset).

Figure 2. Some of the voyages collected for 2018, each colour corresponds to a different ship.

For simplicity, the information on ships’ headings collected from AIS data is not used in this work; instead, the relative wave direction is considered uniform, as recommended in [IACS, 2022]. To force this assumption, we thus duplicate the voyage obtained for each relative heading considered. A discretisation of 30° is used.

2.2. Ship responses

The responses considered in this work are linear loads on a database of ships. The loads investigated are summarised in Table 1.a, and the ships used in Table 1.b. The linear calculations have been performed using 3D-BEM theory (HydroStar Chen [2004]), using 5 knots speed [IACS, 2022].

RAO label	Description	Ship type	Full	Ballast
VBM	Vertical Bending Moment at 0.5L	Tanker	16	11
HBM	Horizontal Bending Moment at 0.5L	Bulk and cargo	19	16
VSF	Vertical Shear Force, at 0.25L	Container-ship	21	10
Pitch	Pitch motion	LNG	5	0
Acc. Surge	Surge acceleration	LPG	5	0
Acc. Sway	Sway acceleration	Roro	3	0
Pressure wl	Waterline pressure at 0.5L	Passenger-ship	5	0
Roll	Roll motion	Total	74	37

(a) Responses

(b) Ships

Table 1. Ship responses used used in the analysis.

In the following, we will see that several behaviors related to the serial correlation can be explained by the wave period to which ship responses are sensitive. To formalize this, we use here a characteristic wave period, hereafter noted T_{cr} , that quantifies the wave period that excites the most the response. This T_{cr} comes from the wave parameter concept, which is detailed in de Hauteclocque and Derbanne [2016]. Although the exact definition is not of paramount importance for the current paper, for the sake of completeness, the procedure to derive this characteristic period is here briefly described.

For each response, the steps are as follows:

1. The 25-years response is calculated with different Froude scales. I.e. the response is calculated for different ship lengths.
2. Responses are scaled with L^{n-1} . Where n is the Froude dimension of the response (e.g. translations have $n = 1$, moments $n = 4$).
3. The length that provides the maximum response is extracted and noted L_{ref} .
4. A characteristic length L_{cr} is calculated for the response as $L * L_c / L_{ref}$ where L_c is an arbitrary length, that characterise the scatter-diagram.
5. To get a more intuitive dimension, L_{cr} is converted to period using the dispersion relationship :

$$T_{cr} = \sqrt{2\pi L_{cr} / g}$$

The characteristic period T_{cr} is thus defined up to the arbitrary constant L_c ; in this work, the reference scatter-diagram used in step 1 is from IACS [2001], together with $L_c = 486m$ so that absolute values of T_{cr} are consistent with previously published work [Austefjord et al., 2023]. That being said, what really matters is not the absolute value of the characteristic periods, but rather the relative differences between those periods.

A simpler choice could have been to select the period that maximizes the transfer function, but this is not as representative; RAO can have maxima at high frequencies that do not contribute to the actual response once the environment is accounted for. The characteristic period for all investigated ships and responses are plotted in Figure 3.. For responses other than roll, the characteristic response period is highly correlated to the vessel length; besides, some response types can be sensitive to long waves (e.g. Vertical Bending Moment or surge acceleration), or short waves (e.g. Horizontal Bending Moment or pressure at the waterline). For roll motion, the characteristic period is closely related to the resonance frequency.

Finally, we should emphasise that, in this work, the use of T_{cr} is only for plots and explanatory purposes. The conclusions drawn here do not depend on the precise definition of T_{cr} .

Figure 3. Characteristic response period for the database.

3. Long term approach

3.1. Scatter-diagram

Once data are collected in wave height and period bins, normalization provides us with the discretised joint distribution $f_{ss} = p(H_s, T0m1)$. Long-term analysis can then be conducted; the equations can be

found in classic textbooks or standards (see for instance Bureau Veritas [2019]) and are here summarized.

Notation	Description
RT_z	Mean up-crossing response period
D_{ss}	Stable sea-state duration, typically 3 hours
$P_C(X)$	Cycle non-exceedance probability. i.e. probability of not exceeding X on a cycle randomly picked in all sea-states.
$P_C(X ss)$	Cycle non-exceedance probability, knowing the sea-state. i.e. probability of not exceeding X on each response cycle, in a given sea-state.
$P_{st}(X)$	Non-exceedance probability on a duration D_{ss} , on a randomly picked sea-state.
$P_{st}(X ss)$	Short term non-exceedance probability, knowing the sea-state i.e. probability of not exceeding X in duration D_{ss} on a given sea-state.
$P_{LT}(X, T)$	Long term non-exceedance probability. i.e. probability of not exceeding X in duration T (typically 25 years)
$f_{ss} = f(H_s, T0m1)$	Joint density probability of sea-condition.
$p_{ss} = p(H_s, T0m1)$	Probability of sea-condition : scatter-diagram

Table 2. Notation used

Combining short-term and long-term probabilities, the short-term non-exceedance probability of X is given by:

$$P_{st}(X) = \int_{ss} P_{st}(X|ss) * f_{ss}(ss) d_{ss} \quad (1)$$

or in discrete form:

$$P_{st}(X) = \sum_i P_{st}(X|ss_i) * p_{ss}(ss_i) \quad (2)$$

Considering all sea states as independent:

$$P_{LT}(X, T) = P_{st}(X)^{T/D_{ss}} = \left[\sum_i P_{st}(X|ss_i) * p_{ss}(ss_i) \right]^{T/D_{ss}} \quad (3)$$

Then, considering cycles independent, **within a sea state**:

$$P_{st}(X|ss) = P_C(X|ss)^{N_{ss}} = P_C(X|ss)^{\frac{D_{ss}}{RT_z}} \quad (4)$$

$$P_{LT}(X, T) = \left[\sum_i P_C(X|ss_i)^{\frac{D_{ss_i}}{RT_{z_i}}} * p_{ss}(ss_i) \right]^{T/D_{ss}} \quad (5)$$

Furthermore, using the Bayes theorem, we can calculate the probability of a given sea state knowing that a given response is exceeded (sometimes referred to as 'contribution coefficients'):

$$P(ss_i|x > X) = \frac{(1 - P_C(X|ss_i)^{D_{ss}/RT_z}) * p_{ss_i}}{\sum_i P_{st}(X|ss_i) * p_{ss}(ss_i)} \quad (6)$$

Extreme value can also be expressed in cycle exceedance probability P_C

$$P_C(X) = 1 - \frac{n_{exceedance}(X)}{n_{exceedance}(0)} = 1 - \overline{Rtz} * \sum \frac{p_{ss}(ss_i)}{RT_{z_i}} * (1 - P_C(X|ss_i)) \quad (7)$$

$$\overline{Rtz} = \frac{1}{\sum \frac{p_{ss}(ss_i)}{RT_{z_i}}} \quad (8)$$

Considering all cycles independent, we thus obtain the following approximation of $P_{LT}(X, T)$:

$$P'_{LT}(X, T) = P_C(X)^{T/\overline{Rt_z}} \quad (9)$$

A common practice is to define the return period RP using $P_C(X_{RP}) = 1 - 1/N(RP)$, where $N(RP)$ is the number of cycles in RP . As all cycles are considered independent in that approach, the non-exceedance probability of X_{RP} can be calculated as:

$$P'(X_{RP}, RP) = (1 - 1/N(RP))^{N(RP)} \xrightarrow{N \rightarrow +\infty} 1/e \quad (10)$$

The convergence to $1/e$ is very quick (with $N=1000$, error is less than 0.1%, and we are rather looking at order of magnitude of $N=10^8$). This leads us to a more consistent definition of the return period. The return period RP of the return value X_{RP} is defined such that:

$$P_{LT}(X_{RP}, RP) = 1/e \quad (11)$$

Generally, the problem in defining the return period as $P(X_{RP}) = 1 - 1/N$ is that N (the number of "events") is not always clear: is it the total number of events, or the number of independent events? If the later, how is the independence defined? On the other hand, Eq. 11 clearly define the return period, without any ambiguity: different approximations of RP with different assumptions on the dependence can then be made and compared, using the same definition.

Using a scatter-diagram approach, two alternatives for the evaluation of RP are thus given by Eq. 3 and 9. Furthermore, using Eq. 3, a choice must be made on the duration D_{ss} . This D_{ss} represents the duration over which sea conditions are considered stable, but also independent from its neighbours. Typical value is $3h$. Sensitivity to this value is analyzed in Section 4.. On the other hand, formulation 9 considers all response cycles as independent and does not require any addition assumption. When D_{ss} is small (of the order of RT_z), Eq. 9 and Eq. 3 rely on similar assumptions and thus provide the same results. Figure 4. verifies this statement.

Figure 4. Comparison of Eq. 9 and Eq. 3 when $D_{ss} = 10s$

Besides the serial correlation issue, binning the data leads to rounding approximations. Figure 5.a compares the results of using bins of 1 meter and 1 second to those using infinitely small bins (i.e. no binning, but still an assumption of independent sea states) on the 25-year response. The relative error ranges from 0.2 to 2.5%, which is small, but not completely negligible compared to the serial correlation effect investigated here. Figure 5.b investigates the error for various bin sizes; with a 0.2m and 0.2s bin size for H_s and T_{0m1} respectively, the RMSE is below 0.2% and considered acceptable for the current

application. In the following, for conciseness, the scatter-diagram approaches thus use the results with these fine (0.2m/0.2s) bins; this shows negligible approximation and allows for fast evaluation of Equation 3 and 9.

(a) Effect of the 1s and 1m discretisation.

(b) Convergence.

Figure 5. Effect of the scatter diagram discretisation on the 25-year long-term estimates.

3.2. Peak-Over-Threshold

Using the time series, declustering can be applied to the data to ensure independence of events; peak-over-threshold or block maxima approaches can be used to extract extreme at any given return period [Coles, 2001].

In our work, the input is a time series of sea conditions given as H_s and T_{0m1} every 3 hours and response RAOs. Assuming a narrow-banded spectrum, the short-term distribution on a given sea-state is given by the Rayleigh distribution [Molin, 2002]. Assuming cycles independent within a sea state, the short-term maxima are then distributed as $P_C^{D_{ss}/Rtz}$. We can thus reconstruct the time series of maximum response by calculating m_0 and m_2 on every sea state and, each time, sampling a short-term maximum from the Rayleigh distribution to the power D_{ss}/Rtz . The obtained time series is then de-clustered by selecting maxima on a moving window of 2 days (larger than typical storm duration.).

It is acknowledged that this de-clustering is not complete: several vessels can be in the same location at a given time, thus depending on the same storms. It is nevertheless assumed that the remaining correlation is small compared to the initial one; this will be further discussed in Section 4.4..

By applying the above process, the information on the short-term variability, which is perfectly known, is not fully used (only one sample is drawn on each sea state). The sampling uncertainties are thus not as reduced as they could be. To overcome this, the overall process is repeated m_{sht} times, and the long-term extremes obtained are averaged over those m_{sht} samples [Mackay and Johanning, 2018]. In this work, we have used $m_{sht} = 2$ (to limit the CPU cost).

Note that without using declustering, the POT approach should provide the same results as Eq. 3 using $D_{ss}=3$ hours; this is indeed the case, the root mean square difference over all responses is about 0.1%.

4. Results

4.1. Effect of the serial correlation

Approaches to assess long-term extreme accounting or not for serial correlation have been introduced in section 3.2. and 3.1. respectively. We now compare the results of the different approaches on the database of ship responses. The POT approach that uses declustering is here considered the reference to which the different scatter-diagram formulations are compared.

Figure 6. Effect of the serial correlation long-term distribution

Figure 6.a and 6.b show illustrations for two responses. It appears that, while the two responses are calculated in the same environment, the effect of the serial correlation is very different between the two. At $RP = 25$ years, when all cycles are considered independent (Eq. 9) overestimates the response by 13% for the first response and by only 1% for the second one. When cycles are grouped per sea state, but sea states considered independent (Eq 3), the difference is somewhat reduced: 7% for the first response and 0.6% for the second one. Besides, as expected [Mackay et al., 2021], in every case, the difference reduces when the return period increases.

To get a more general picture, figure 7. shows the error on the 25-year extreme for all the responses considered. The error is plotted against the characteristic period of the response. The effect of neglecting any serial correlation between response cycles ranges from 0% to 15%. In all cases, the error is strongly correlated to the characteristic period of the response, this will be further elaborated in section 4.3..

Figure 7. Effect of the serial correlation on the long-term estimates on the 25-year extremes.

4.2. Correction

The estimates of long-term extreme are overestimated by the scatter diagram approach that considers all cycles as independent (Eq. 9). Grouping response cycles per sea state of duration on which sea states are

typically considered stable ($D_{ss} = 10800s$) reduces the conservative bias but does not remove it completely. We now investigate whether the D_{ss} value can be used as a tuning parameter to emulate the serial correlation of the sea state. Value of 3, 6, 12 and 20 hours are tested; results are presented in Figure 8.. As expected, the long-term estimate decreases when D_{ss} increases. Moreover, for the 25-year response, a value of D_{ss} of 12 hours compensates well for the ignorance of the sea-state correlation; and this consistently across the range of responses.

Note that this value of $D_{ss} = 12$ hours is a calibrated one, and is not expected to be universal. In particular, it is not expected to be the optimum one for different return periods or climates very different from the North-Atlantic. For instance, in tropical climates, where long-term variability is larger due to cyclones, the effect of serial correlation is expected to increase as well, and the value of D_{ss} tuned on North-Atlantic conditions might not be perfect. Despite these limitations, this pragmatic approach is considered relevant to several application cases, and is still on the conservative side (see for instance Figure 8.a for the 1 year return period).

Figure 8. Effect of the sea state duration D_{ss} on long term extremes.

4.3. Long-term variability.

In Mackay et al. [2021], the effect of the serial correlation was found to depend mainly on two ingredients. The first is the shape of the time series and how clustered the extremes are. The second ingredient is the heaviness of the distribution tail and the relative weight of the short-term variability against the long-term one.

In our context, the time series "shape" is similar from one response to another (as there is a unique underlying metocean variables time series). Besides, the short-term variability is also very close from one response to the other: all response cycles are Rayleigh distributed. The only explanation left to explain the differences in behaviour observed in Figure 7. is thus the long-term variability. To elaborate on this assumption, the long-term variability of the response is formalized as the relative slope of the long-term distribution, with log scale for the return period (Eq 12). Figure 9.a, which shows a tight relationship between s and the effect of the serial correlation clearly validates the hypothesis.

$$s(RP) = \frac{dx(RP)}{x(RP)d \log(RP)} \quad (12)$$

Figure 9. Effect of the long term variability of the response (s)

s is then plotted against the characteristic period of each response in Figure 9.b; the correlation is very strong. The sensitivity of the long-term variability to the characteristic response period can, in turn, be explained by looking at the scatter diagram. Figure 10.a shows the IFORM contours calculated from the model that underlies the IACS Recommendation 34 scatter-diagram [IACS, 2022], which is fitted on the very same data used in this paper. At low wave periods, the contours are close together, which is related to the physical limit on wave steepness. The variability is larger at large wave periods. This behaviour can also be illustrated by looking at contours intersected at different wave periods, plotted against the return period (Figure 10.b). The slope is larger as the wave period increases.

Figure 10. Long-term variability - wave only.

4.4. Uncertainties and remaining data correlation.

The data used in this work have a finite duration, leading to sampling uncertainties when assessing extreme. The duration of underlying hindcast data is "only" 7 years, compensated for by a large space coverage: we are not looking only at a single location but at the whole North-Atlantic, seen by many vessels. The concatenated time series (over ships and heading) is about 3000 years long, which seems

sufficient to establish 25 years extreme with good convergence. Admittedly, there is redundancy in this dataset, so it cannot be considered as a true 3000-year time series. As the data are not easily de-clustered, the precise evaluation of the sampling uncertainties is not straightforward. Besides, the outcome of the current work is comparative; the uncertainty on the absolute values is thus not of prime importance.

This paper discusses the effect of accounting for the serial correlation on typical ship responses. To perform this work, we would ideally use the long-time series data (much longer than the return period looked at), for a large number of ships. Such data do not exist, so that we relied on the concatenation of voyages collected over 7 years across the North-Atlantic. We have performed the de-clustering at the time scale of a storm; longer scale correlation thus remains in the data and has not been accounted for (seasonal variability, for instance). The effect of such a longer-scale clustering is not in the scope of the current work.

5. Conclusions

A sensitivity analysis of extreme loads to the assumption of independent sea states has been performed in North-Atlantic wave conditions. The observation was in line with recent literature on the subject [Mackay et al., 2021] : neglecting the serial correlation yields conservative estimates. Moreover, this effect is more significant when the long-term variability is large. On the 25 years return period response typically used in the shipping industry, the overestimation ranges from 0% to 15%. The variation is explained by the characteristic period of the response: the effect is much larger for responses which are sensitive to long waves.

A pragmatic, calibrated approach is then proposed to account for the effect of serial correlation while keeping input as a scatter diagram: considering independent sea states with a duration of 12 hours compensates well for the serial correlation effect and provides long-term estimates that match very well with more refined analysis.

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